

ANALYSIS OF MANAGEMENT AND INNOVATION MANAGEMENT IN LIGHT INDUSTRY

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Abstract. In this article, on the example of light industry, innovation and its management, as well as the scientific and theoretical basis for its improvement, the role of innovation management in the development of the national economy and light industry, advantages and disadvantages, integration of science and production, the share of high-tech production in the industry and its increase stopped.

Keywords: national economy, light industry, innovation, innovation activity, innovation potential, innovation management, technology transfer, venture organizations, new development, innovation commercialization, innovation infrastructure.

Innovation orientation of the economy will be one of the important factors determining the growth and competitiveness of national economies in the future. Limited and increasingly difficult natural resources and unstable global economic and political conditions require an increase in innovative potential.

It is known from the experience of economically developed countries that the formation and development of an innovation-oriented economy is carried out through the state policy aimed at creating favorable conditions for the widespread use of innovative technologies and new developments. One of the important indicators of national and global innovative development in this regard is the ratio of spending on scientific research and development to GDP. Globally, there is a tendency for countries and corporations to increase their spending on scientific research and development, as well as to actively support startups.

The share of high-tech (including medium-tech (high-level)) and knowledge-intensive sectors in GDP in the indicators of the level of technological development of the national economy was 22.8% in 2019, 23.7% in 2020, and slightly decreased in 2021 (23.5%). , increased by 25.7% in 2022, the share of high-tech and science-intensive industries in GDP reached 19.3% in 2019, 20.6% in 2020, 20.5% in 2021, and 22.4% in 2022. the share of output in the added value of the manufacturing industry increased from 1.9 percent in 2019 to 2.3 percent in 2022 (Table 1.1).

Table 1.1

Indicators assessing the level of technological development of the economy (%)

	2019 year	2020 year	2021 year	2022 year
Share of high-tech (medium-tech (high-level)) and science-intensive industries in GDP	22,8	23,7	23,5	25,7
Share of high-tech and science-intensive industries in GDP	19,3	20,6	20,5	22,4
The share of high-tech production in the value added of the producing industry	1,9	2,1	2,8	2,3

Source: prepared by the author based on the statistical collection of science and innovative activity in Uzbekistan.

The light industry of the Uzbekistan, the textile and leather goods industry, which occupies the largest part of its production, was formed in the year of independence. The current association "Uzto‘qimachilik sanoat" was recently established under the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 14, 2017, "In the context of rapid development of textile and sewing industry" PF-5285-con.

New modern management functions and tasks such as strategic forecasting, coordination of scientific-research works, introduction of innovative technologies are given priority in the management structure of "Uzto‘qimachilik sanoat" association. Also, in the decree, the tasks of increasing the share of the textile industry in the economy, increasing the size and quality of the manufactured textile products by reorienting them to the high-tech production of competitive textile products with high added value are defined.

As of January 1, 2024, more than 8,000 economic units specialized in the production of textile products will be operating, of which 11 percent are textile, 89 percent are specialized in the production of sewing and knitting products, and currently there are 2,051 sewing and knitting and textile and machine engineering companies. enterprises are members of the "Uzto‘qimachilik sanoat" association.

According to the decision of the President of Uzbekistan in 2018 "On measures to further encourage the development of leather-shoes and fur industries and increase the export potential", the "Uzbekcharpoyabzali" association was reorganized into the "Uzcharmsanoat" association. Currently, the association includes more than 500 shoe factories with a production capacity of more than 280 million pairs. Although the management structure of the "Uzcharmsanoat" association has a consultant for the prospective development of industries and foreign consultants, the absence of a separate department directly dealing with functions and tasks related to innovations does not fail to have an impact on the effective management of innovations. From this point of view, it is appropriate to include the functions and tasks of working with innovations in the management structure of "Uzcharmsanoat" association.

According to the projects completed in 2023 within the framework of the Innovative Development Strategy, the "Uzto‘qimachilik sanoat" association and the "Uzbekipaksanoati" association were among the 10 most advanced industries with 16 projects each. We can see that in 2023, 30 (14.3%) of the total 209 projects implemented as a result of the integration of science and production belong to the light industry, which is behind the geology, mining and metallurgical industries in terms of integration (Figure 1.1).

Figure 1.1. Integration of science and production

Source: Prepared by the author based on information from the official website of the Innovation Development Agency of Uzbekistan.

The analysis of industrial activity and innovation indicators of enterprises and organizations of economic sectors shows that the state budget funds are limited, the number of innovative funds and the small amount of funds accumulated in them, and the complexity of attracting the private sector show that there is a need to increase their number by supporting and encouraging venture organizations. It should be noted that the active participation of venture investors not only in financing innovations, but also in the management of networks and enterprises plays an important role in reducing risks and ensuring efficiency.

Practice shows that the sustainable development of light canoes today, taking into account the market situation and the constantly recurring changes in consumer behavior, depends to a large extent on innovation management, and its successful application in practice ensures high performance.

First of all, it is appropriate to organize learning and research of innovation management in the field of education. At the same time, after studying the management structure and methods of advanced companies, it is necessary to achieve their application in light industrial enterprises.

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